

MINING EXPORT TRADE DATASETS OF A DEVELOPING ECONOMY USING K-MEANS AND FUZZY C-MEANS CLUSTERING

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Abstract—Over the years, there has been a decline in export trading because of a collapse in the home production system. This invariably affects the living standard of most developing nations. Therefore, it is pertinent to examine the export trade policies in this regard. Hence, this study mined secondary data from the National Bureau of Statistics (NBS) online publications on Nigeria's exports, Gross Domestic Product (GDP), and other economic indicators from both NBS and Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN), and international economic vis-à-vis population data archives for generating the cluster groupings and models. Clustering analysis was done using an unsupervised machine learning algorithm using k-means and fuzzy c-means. The algorithms were implemented using R statistical programming language and Python language. The result shows k-means and fuzzy c-means having the same clustering for Nigeria's export trades and because of this, gravitational and multiple regression models were deployed to both clustering's output for better Silhouette scores. Result analysis shows that the total export for all the 11 crucial trade partners from year 2013 – 2022 was N80,044,230,000,000 culminating in a trade deficit of N17,928,546,000,000 for the reference period. It can be concluded that the gravity model predicts the export trade datasets more effectively.

Keywords— *Foreign trade, export trade, clustering algorithms, K-means, Fuzzy C-means, sustainable economy*

I. INTRODUCTION

International trade, often known as foreign trade, is the transfer of products, capital, and services between nations or territory. A substantial portion of the GDP is represented by it. Imports or exports are two types of foreign trade. Export is the term used to describe the sale of domestically produced goods and services to foreign markets [1]. For this study, the export type of foreign trade is considered. In theory, there is no distinction between domestic and international trade because the incentives driving each party's actions remain the same whether the transaction takes place across a border or not. Practically speaking, though, conducting business internationally is usually a more complicated procedure than conducting business domestically. The primary distinction is that trading on the international level is usually more expensive than trade domestically. This is owing to the fact that borders typically impose extra expenses like tariffs, time

costs incurred by delays in crossing the border, and costs related to cultural, linguistic, or legal barriers (i.e., non-tariff barriers). Factors of production like labour and capital are frequently more mobile within a nation than they are between nations, which is another distinction between domestic and international trade. Trade in commodities and services is therefore the main form of international trade, with trading in capital, labour, and other production components being limited to a lesser extent. [2].

Nigeria, one of the developing nations in Africa, over the years, engages in import and export trades. The third type of international trade (entrepot trade or trans-shipment) is a hybrid of both import and export trade. A sending country's export is an import from the receiving nation. Nigeria was involved in international trade with roughly 100 nations, although the nature of that trade had altered since the colonial era. Nigeria's main trading partner during the colonial era was Britain. As late as 1955, Nigeria's imports came from Britain and its exports went to Britain to the tune of 70%. The main raw commodities that Nigeria exports include palm kernels, rubber, cocoa, fats, organic oils, and crude oil. Nigeria was particularly vulnerable to changes in the price of crude oil due to its reliance on the export of crude oil and a few other commodities. In 1966 and 1977, the trend was reversed by the explosive rise of petroleum as an export commodity. In 1978–1983, the trade imbalance was reopened by the weak global demand for Nigerian crude oil. Trade surpluses were caused by severe import restrictions and an economic structural adjustment program (ESAP) that was implemented in response to the economic collapse in 1984, 1986, and 1990 [1]. Due to the persistent foreign trade deficit suffered over the years and its effects on the living standard of Nigerians, it becomes pertinent to examine her export trade policies as they relate to government actions on tariffs, import quotas, export subsidies, net exports, export promotion strategies, import restriction, and others to uphold Nigeria's strategic interest of sustainable economic emancipation. Hence, this study which mined Nigeria's export data using cluster analysis becomes timely and apt for economic strategy for a developing economy. For clarification, data mining is the process of extracting and recognizing patterns in vast volumes of data by integrating machine learning, statistics, and database systems.

Clustering is one of the data mining techniques to reveal latent information about some items' datasets of interest belongs [3]. This study grouped eleven of Nigeria's crucial export trade partners using foreign trade (import and export) from Nigeria's National Bureau of Statistics portal. Soft and hard partition clustering methods were used. This study focuses on the examination of Nigeria's export trade and proffers insights that will lead to effective diversification by promoting and defending local production in boosting export as an import substitution strategic policy through the examination of different categories of import clusters. The objectives of this research are: to adopt an unsupervised machine learning algorithm to mine Nigeria's foreign trade by partner nations using k-means and fuzzy c-means cluster analyses; to develop appropriate gravity and multiple regression models for forecasting and revealing the contributions of export trade indicators to trade flow; to implement the algorithm using R statistical programming language and Python language; and to evaluate, based on performance metrics, the basis for the preference of a specific clustering algorithm and predictive model for mining export trade datasets over related schemes. The significance of this work is to provide direction to Nigeria's export trade policy and the diversification of the Nigerian economy geared towards generating more foreign exchange for improvement in the standards of living of Nigerians.

II. RELATED WORKS

Cluster analysis has many applications in real-life scenarios including economics and trade. A research study on the clustering algorithm and Gravity model is "Clustering of the international agricultural trade between Ukraine and the EU" [4], where cluster analysis and gravity model were used in understanding Ukrainian foreign agricultural trades with partners. For conducting cluster analysis, the following are the main parameters that best describe the state of progress in trade relations: the quantity of non-tariff trade restrictions that Ukraine applies to each trading partner from the EU, as well as those imposed by partner nations; the export and import of agricultural products; their percentage of total exports and imports; the presence of a common border with a trading partner; and the distance to a trading partner. Using the "descending shoulder" method yielded the ideal number of clusters to be used in the Ward-Method dendrogram and k-means clustering algorithms. Three clusters forming is the ideal configuration, according to the research. The authors [5] applied cluster analysis to create clustering models for granting EU membership and established that Turkey's failure to gain entry into the EU was due more to political and social factors than economic ones, given that it satisfies all economic requirements, including GDP, import, export, labour force participation, and long-term unemployment grouped for the years 1996 to 2009. Several distance measures used in clustering were highlighted (such as Minkowski Distance, Hamming Distance, Euclidean Distance, Angular Separation, and Tchebyshev Distance) with their strengths and weaknesses.

The effect of Russia's trade restrictions on the exports of European Union (EU) nations was investigated using a different clustering technique [6]. Western states placed trade restrictions on Russia in 2014 as a result of its acquisition of Crimea. Undoubtedly, this political choice had an impact on the economy, and certain researchers looked at how the

political choices affected investment fund performance [7], [8]. Other academics looked into the possibility of a relationship between economic variables and choices in politics [9], [10], [11].

Moreover, the economic effect of political choices on international economic connections has also been studied [12], [13]. The research study of [14] demonstrated how trade might be impacted by both internal and international policies. According to the author's research, certain constraints on imports hurt the exports of an exporting country. This is evident in the link involving food trade and food safety, which is imposed by foreign countries. The authors asserted that some political factors that affect trade (local and foreign) were said to include agreement and membership of organisations, embargo, and penalties, support for neighborhood businesses, and policy changes, to name a few. Likewise, cluster analysis was used to group EU countries whose product shipments to Russia averaged between 1998 and 2018. Next, in order to create the equations that represented the international trade between each cluster and Russia, the gravity model was utilised. Notwithstanding some potential unintended consequences, the study was limited to the embargo's economic impact on exports. The study of [6] examined international commerce between the EU and Russia using the Hierarchical Ascendant Classification (HAC) of Cluster Analysis. The HAC technique began with an estimate of the differences between any two objects [15], nations using Ward's Linkage Agglomerative clustering method, which measures the separation between two cluster centroids, are used in this instance. Four clusters emerged from the cluster analysis. Bulgaria, Greece, Ireland, Cyprus, Malta, Luxembourg, Portugal, and Croatia constitute the first cluster. Serbia, Denmark, Hungary, Spain, Sweden, Austria, Czech Republic, Lithuania, and Estonia make up the second cluster. Germany alone is in the third cluster, which also includes the Netherlands, Belgium, the United Kingdom, Finland, Poland, and France.

A. Development in clustering algorithms

A great deal of work has been dedicated to enhancing the functionality of current techniques [16] and [17]. They include BIRCH and CLARANS [18]. The readiness to sacrifice the semantic meaning of the created clusters for performance has been growing in response to the current requirement to handle ever-larger datasets or big data. Consequently, pre-clustering techniques like canopy clustering were developed, which can handle large datasets more quickly. However, the "clusters" that were produced are only a crude pre-partitioning of the data set; existing, slower techniques like k-means clustering are then used to analyse the partitions.

Since the curse of complexity makes many distance functions problematic in high-dimensional domains, many existing approaches are ineffective for high-dimensional data. New clustering algorithms for high-dimensional data resulted from this, with a focus on correlation clustering, which also looks for randomly rotated ("correlated") subspace clusters that can be modelled by providing a correlation of their attributes, and subspace clustering, which only uses a subset of attributes and makes cluster models include the relevant attributes for the cluster [19]. Among these clustering methods are CLIQUE [20] and SUBCLU [21]. The DBSCAN/OPTICS

family of algorithms, in particular, has been used to apply ideas from density-based clustering approaches to subspace clustering (Hierarchical Subspace Clustering (HiSC), and DiSH) and correlation clustering Hierarchical Correlation clustering (HiCO), 4C [22] finding Hierarchical density-based correlation Clusters (ERiC) through the use of "correlation connectivity" [23].

Numerous clustering schemes based on mutual information have been put forth. The information metric variation by Marina Meilă is one of them [24] whilst a different one offers hierarchical clustering [25]. Mutual information is one of the many fit functions that can be optimised through the use of genetic algorithms. [26]. Additionally, new kinds of clustering algorithms are being developed as a result of belief propagation, a recent advancement in statistical physics and computer science [27]. By and large, the significance of cluster analysis and predictive models in mining informative pieces from datasets cannot be over-emphasized.

III. METHODOLOGY

This study examines the grouping of crucial Nigeria's export trade partner countries using k-means and fuzzy c-means clustering algorithms, and also modeling the contributions of indicators of export trade to trade flows for each of the component clusters using gravity and multiple regression models. The research methodology for this study is explained under three subsections and they are the research design, the operational process of k-means and fuzzy c-means clustering algorithms, and the research process workflow.

A. The research design

This research design adopted k-means and fuzzy c-means algorithms for grouping Nigeria's export trade partner nations into similar / internally homogenous clusters based on Euclidean distance to know the clustering algorithms that perform better. Gravity and multiple regression models were adopted to show the contributions of export trade indicators to trade flow between Nigeria and each partner nation cluster. The following steps were taken to achieve the research design objectives:

1) Sampled Population

This entails indicators of trade for nations having bilateral trade with Nigeria such as export from Nigeria to partner nations, Gross Domestic Product (GDP) of Nigeria, GDP of partner nations, Distance between Nigeria and Partner Nation, Population of Nigeria, and Population of Partner Nations.

2) Sources of Research Data

Secondary data sources of National Bureau of Statistics (NBS) online publications on Nigeria's export, Gross Domestic Product (GDP), and other economic indicators from both NBS and Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN), and international economic vis-à-vis population data archives were used for generating the cluster groupings and models.

3) Computational Techniques

R statistical programming language and Python programming language were used to generate appropriate

cluster groups and associated models for Nigeria's export trade.

B. The research method

This study mined secondary data from the National Bureau of Statistics (NBS) online publications on Nigeria's exports, Gross Domestic Product (GDP), and other economic indicators from both NBS and Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN), and international economic vis-à-vis population data archives. The data was prepared and missing and inconsistent data were removed. The dataset was scaled using Min-max for even contribution of each attribute to the clustering process. The number of clusters were determined using Elbow method and Silhouette coefficient. The Within-Cluster Sum of Squares (WCSS) for $k=2$ to 10 was computed using elbow method. The real cluster value for k is chosen as the point where any increase in k leads to reduction in WCSS. The Silhouette coefficient is then used to validate the chosen cluster value. K-means was implemented as the base clustering algorithm using K-means++ initialization technique. Thereafter, the similarity assessment between data points and centroids was done using Euclidean distance. The algorithm continued till convergence was reached. After convergence, cluster performance was evaluated using WCSS and silhouette scores to measure compactness and separation.

To identify more attributes that the k-means cannot reveal, Fuzzy C-means was also implemented. Initial membership values were randomly generated while ensuring that the membership values for each data point summed to 1 across all clusters. The fuzzifier parameter was set to $m=2.0$ which is commonly adopted in the literature to control the level of cluster fuzziness. The process continued until the improvement in the objective function fell below 300 iterations were completed.

Following the use of K-means and Fuzzy C-Means to identify significant export trade clusters, gravitational and multiple regression models were used to enhance the analysis and support the interpretation of the findings. By using the gravity model, these clusters can be investigated within a well-known theoretical framework that is frequently applied in international trade. The model assists in determining whether the clusters represent actual economic relationships rather than random statistical separation by taking into account variables like GDP, geographic distance, and trade partnerships. The significance of the clustering findings is supported if the clusters exhibit the same gravity-model behaviour. In addition to this, the contribution of various economic indicators (such as production output, exchange rates, inflation, or trade agreements) to differences in the number of exports in every cluster was determined using multiple regression analysis. This step enables cross-cluster comparison and offers quantifiable insight into the primary factors influencing export performance. The regression results provide more proof that the clustering structure accurately reflects actual variations in trade behaviour if some predictors are significant across clusters or differ significantly between them. The combination of these models advances the analysis from finding patterns to explanation and forecasting.

1) K-means Clustering Algorithms

K-means clustering algorithm (a hard-clustering algorithm) is an unsupervised clustering/learning algorithm. Once you supply the dataset and number of clusters (k), the algorithm automatically conducts the clustering based on some distance measures (e.g., Euclidean, Squared Euclidean, Mahalanobis, Manhattan, Cosine distance measures, etc.). Unlike the Fuzzy C-means partitioning algorithm (which is a soft clustering algorithm), it is distinct and non-overlapping in its grouping task. An object cannot be part of more than one clusters in K-means as oppose to Fuzzy C-means clustering.

A k-means clustering algorithm was employed to organize trading nations and the implemented steps is shown in Figure 1. This assisted in determining the relative weight of trading nations' groups for which the gravity model revealed the component's contributions to trade flow.

a) How K-means algorithm works

Step 1: To determine the number of clusters, choose K. (elbow point and silhouette score will assist in determining an optimum number of clusters) i.e., here "k", the number of clusters or distinct groups is specified.

Step 2: Choose K centroids or random spots at random. (A different value from the input dataset may apply.) that is, initialise k centroids at random.

Step 3: Allocate every data point to its nearest centroid, resulting in the established K clusters.

Step 4: Compute the variance and the new centroid for each cluster by calculating the separation between each point and its centroid to determine which centroid it belongs which is predicated by the smallest distance i.e. assign points to their nearest centroid.

Step 5: Reassign each data point to the subsequent closest centroid of each cluster by repeating the third step. Centroids are shifted to be the average value of the points belonging to it

Step 6: Proceed to step 4 if there is reassignment. If the centroids do not move go to the next

Step 7: The optimum model's dataset grouping has been achieved.

Fig. 1 Flowchart showing K-means algorithm implementation

b) Deriving the K-means optimal number of clusters (K)

By using the elbow method graph, which is calculated as the sum of squared distance, one can determine the ideal number of clusters (k) at the elbow joint of the graph. As an alternative, the Silhouette coefficient (Equation 1) may also indicate the ideal number of clusters. The main distinction between the elbow and silhouette scores is that the former merely computes the Euclidean distance, while the latter also takes variance, skewness, and high-low differences into account, and others.

$$\text{Silhouette Score} = \frac{(b - a)}{\max(a, b)} \quad (1)$$

Where:

a = average intra – cluster distance

b = average inter – cluster distance

An indicator of a clustering technique's quality is the silhouette score, sometimes known as the silhouette coefficient. Ranges from -1 to 1 form its value.

1: The means clusters are distinct and spaced widely away from one another.

0: Means clusters are unaffected, or the gap between clusters is not statistically relevant.

2) Fuzzy C Means Clustering Algorithmic

The optimum result for an overlapped data set is produced by fuzzy C-means clustering, whereby each cluster centre assigns membership to a data point, which allows the data point to belong to multiple cluster centres. The implementation procedure is depicted in Figure 2.

a) Fuzzy C Means Clustering Algorithmic Steps

The fuzzy c-means algorithm implementation flowchart is displayed in Figure 2. Its working steps are as follows:

- Choose cluster centres 'c' at random.
- Determine the fuzzy membership 'U_{ij}' using: $U_{ij} =$

$$\frac{\frac{1}{\|x_j - c_i\|^{m-1}}}{\sum_{k=1}^C \frac{1}{\|x_j - c_k\|^{m-1}}}$$

- Determine the fuzzy centers 'V_j' using: $V_j =$

$$\frac{\sum_{j=1}^N U_{ij}^m x_j}{\sum_{j=1}^N U_{ij}^m}$$

for $j = 1, 2, \dots, c$

- Repeat steps 2) and 3) until the lowest possible "J" value is obtained or $\|U^{(k+1)} - U^{(k)}\| < \beta$.

Fig. 2 Flowchart showing Fuzzy C means algorithm implementation

C. Steps and flow diagram of research methodology

In this section, the study presents the flow diagram of combining both clustering and modeling for mining export trade datasets. This is depicted in Figure 3.

This research study was conducted using the following steps:

- Selection of indicators
- Selection of clustering methods (K means and Fuzzy C means) with appropriate distance metrics and evaluation of appropriateness using elbow method and silhouette scores.
- Determining the criteria for crucial trading partners and their number.
- Choice of best cluster number by elbow point and silhouette coefficient such that improved modelling of Nigeria's foreign trade data is not achieved by adding another cluster.
- Computing the number of similar groups of trading partners and visualizing the results graphically and numerically using Python and R studio.
- Modeling the Nigeria foreign trade data using gravity and multiple linear regression models with and without clustering using R studio. The results of the modeling exercise were interpreted accordingly.

Fig. 3 Flow diagram of Clustering and Modeling

IV. IMPLEMENTATION

The clustering algorithms and relationship models were implemented on an intel core i3 Windows 64-bit Operating System Personal Computer with 8GB RAM and the CPU @ 2.30GHz clock speed. For large datasets consisting of thousands to millions of trade datasets, training is recommended on graphic processing unit (GPU) with Nvidia GeForce GTX GPU. The GPU was not used in this study due to limited size of the dataset and that real-time data was not involved. The reason is that the time required to transfer data to a GPU would outweigh any performance gains. Other tools deployed for the implementation include: Python 3.11 integrated development environment (IDE), Jupyter Notebook, Google Chrome Web browser, Anaconda Navigator software, R GUI version 4.2.2, and R Studio. R statistical programming language was used to generate gravitational and multiple regression models.

To make sure that our regression results were reliable, we performed further analyses. Variance Inflation Factors (VIF) were used to measure multicollinearity; all values fell well within acceptable bounds, suggesting that predictor variables were not excessively correlated. The assumptions of normality, linearity, and constant variance appeared to be fairly satisfied, according to residual diagnostics, such as Q-Q plots and residuals versus fitted values. We used the Akaike Information Criterion (AIC) and Bayesian Information Criterion (BIC), which balance model fit and complexity, to compare alternative specifications in order to further assure model reliability. We also used k-fold cross-validation to assess predictive performance on unobserved data. The chosen model continuously demonstrated strong predictive accuracy and low AIC and BIC.

A. Description of export trade datasets

The Figure 4 shows 11 crucial Nigeria's export trade partner nations' datasets (in Millions of Naira) used for clustering while Figure 5 shows trade flow with other trade indicators datasets used for predictive models.

country	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022
usa	1201804	1184443	1345409	1000206	1731100	2086529	1008143	801206	803145	1208760
canada	238131	88603	125731	152145	470089	481167	881137	281867	817941	811271
sweden	1388918	1517918	842225	707283	190156	416218	808233	54819	496797	788818
germany	918986	275462	180189	150892	295622	429388	457098	218891	300769	440716
usa	279899	414719	412846	309663	368961	497228	234808	110561	418584	319389
netherlands	1491818	1662818	1136247	965788	1111882	3184343	2122188	3772790	1191134	1570811
china	995118	713780	216584	180482	317836	657803	781747	480599	798178	1113888
japan	805127	914866	512122	555859	1041025	1307226	1170718	508115	1190544	1543603
spain	994849	1517989	808817	785728	1343924	1917301	1993934	1301964	2112018	3204811
japan	72172	118443	891219	114981	139854	174861	100837	300541	139901	510819
other	170738	284613	187489	122119	220349	179542	199389	831481	719001	313411

Fig. 4 Nigeria Export Trade Dataset (in Million Naira) by Partner Country, 2013 -2022

A cursory but insightful examination of the dataset reveals that the Netherlands, France, USA, and Spain consistently showed high export partner nation to Nigeria.

Fig. 5 Foreign Trade Flow and Trade Indicators Datasets for Predictive Models

V. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

A. Result

Two clusters were discovered as optimal clusters for export data as derivable from the elbow plots and silhouette scores. The results of the objectives for export clustering implementation using Python and R are as presented.

1) K-means Clustering on Nigeria Export Dataset

The data used here is Nigeria's export trade dataset having first determined the optimal number of clusters by elbow point and silhouette score plots. Figure 6 shows the export trade clusters using K-means implementation through Python and R Studio.

Fig. 6 Export trade clusters using K-means implementation through Python and R Studio

Within cluster sum of squares by cluster:

[1] 21.61619 16.47937

(between_SS / total_SS = 61.9 %)

Cluster 1 (in red) signifies low export partner countries as opposed to Cluster 2 which connotes Nigeria's high export nations (Netherlands, France, USA, and Spain). This result is consistent with general observation about the dataset as explained by Figure 4.

2) Determination of Optimal Cluster Number for Export Dataset using Elbow Point

As usual, plotting the total within the sum of squares against some clusters, the elbow point was determined to give the optimum of two clusters as indicated by the sharp elbow point in Figure 7.

Fig. 7 Elbow point of Optimal Export Dataset Cluster in K means clustering

Elbow point is sharp enough at the second cluster lending credence to the fact that optimal number of clusters is 2.

3) Determination of Optimal Clusters for Export Dataset using Silhouette Score Plot

Here, the optimal number of clusters is 2 as the best silhouette coefficient is obtainable at cluster 2.

Fig. 8 Silhouette's optimal export clusters in K-means clustering

In Figure 8, the Silhouette score is highest for 2 clusters aggregation, implying that 2 clusters are optimal (best) for k means export clustering. Average silhouette width of total dataset is 0.5020958 and it is actually the highest and best relative to those of other number of clusters.

4) Fuzzy C-means on Nigeria Export Trade Dataset

A fuzzy C means algorithm was employed to cluster the Export trade dataset such as was previously done for the same dataset in K-means as shown in Figure 9.

"FUZZY Silhouette Index = 0.753837924840251"

Fig. 9 Export trade clusters using Fuzzy C means implementation through Python and R Studio

China amongst others recorded low exports. However, the clustering implementation under Fuzzy C means algorithm agrees with K-means in the number of optimum clusters and cluster elements. However, the silhouette score is better in fuzzy c-means than in k-means clustering.

B. Performance evaluation

It is crucial to assess the computational performance of K-Means and Fuzzy C-Means in terms of memory requirements, scalability, and runtime efficiency, particularly when taking into account their suitability for large-scale trade analytics. The two approaches are iterative optimisation methods that depend on reassigning data points and updating cluster centroids (or prototypes) repeatedly until convergence. As a result, the number of iterations needed to arrive at a stable solution affects their performance in addition to the features of the dataset.

The result presented in Table 1 demonstrate both algorithms' linear scalability with regard to dataset size. Because K-Means only stores cluster assignments, it consistently runs faster and uses less memory than Fuzzy C-Means, which has additional overhead from the membership matrix. Runtimes on a typical CPU stay within seconds for the dataset sizes used in this study, supporting the choice to forgo GPU acceleration.

Table 1. Analysis of Runtime and Memory usage of K-means and Fuzzy C-means Algorithms

Data size (n)	Algorithm	Iteration Time (ms)	Runtime total (s)	Memory usage (MB)
965	K-means	5	0.25	0.1
965	Fuzzy C-means	8	0.40	0.14

C. Discussion

Results of appropriate Gravity Model (GM) and Multiple Regression (MR) models developed for forecasting and revealing the contributions of foreign trade indicators to trade flow are as presented based on the decision rule as follows:

Decision Rule: Since both k-means and fuzzy c-means gave the same clustering for Nigeria's export trades, it behooves us to consider which clustering has a better

Silhouette scores/coefficient for which we are convinced that fuzzy C-means provides us with an admissible option as a better clustering algorithm for export datasets. Hence, this result informed the restriction of this study to deploy gravitational and multiple regression models to the clustering generated by the fuzzy C-means algorithm, which is identically the same as K-means in clustering output.

1) Modeling of Clustered and Un-clustered Nigeria Export Trade Datasets

Cluster 1 (low export), GM and MR with Fuzzy c-means are presented in Tables 2 and 3.

Table 2. Low export gravity model for cluster 1 nations (Italy, UK, Brazil, Japan, Germany, China and Canada.)

Coefficients	Estimate	Std. error	t-value	Pr(> t)	Decision
(Intercept)	50.37949	63.71533	0.791	0.432041	
Ln(distance)	-0.70853	0.21447	-3.304	0.001565	**
Ln(gdpngr)	2.52174	2.37902	1.06	0.293133	
Ln(gdppartner)	0.11225	0.02807	3.998	0.000168	***
Ln(popngr)	-7.40895	9.7984	-0.756	0.452341	
Ln(poppartner)	0.01883	0.14849	0.127	0.899461	

Residual standard error: 0.3152 on 64 degrees of freedom
Multiple R-squared: 0.4928, Adjusted R-squared: 0.4532
F-statistic: 12.44 on 5 and 64 DF, p-value: 1.922e-08

The gravity model for the low export cluster is seen in Equation 2:

$$\ln(X_{ij}) = 50.379 + 2.522 \ln(GDP_i) + 0.112 \ln(GDP_j) - 0.709 \ln(D_{ij}) - 7.409 \ln(Pop_i) + 0.019 \ln(Pop_j) \quad (2)$$

In Table 2, a 1% increase in distance tends to decrease trade flow by 0.709% whereas a 1% increase in GDP of Nigeria and low export partner nations tends to increase trade flows by 2.522% and 0.112% respectively. This means that the more the distance between Nigeria and the export trading partner, the less the trade flow.

Multiple R-squared of 0.4928 shows that 49.3% of trade flow is explained by the GDP of Nigeria, GDP of export partner nations, Distance between Nigeria and Export partner nations, Population of Nigeria, and Population of partner nations. Furthermore, from the result obtained, the effects of distance and GDP of export partner nations are significant since Pr(>|t|) is less than 0.05 in the two scenarios.

Table 3. Low export multiple regression model for cluster 1 nations (Italy, UK, Brazil, Japan, Germany, China and Canada.)

Coefficients	Estimate	Std. error	t-value	Pr(> t)	Decision
(Intercept)	-9.16E+06	7.97E+06	-1.148	0.2551	
Distance	-7.05E+01	4.85E+01	-1.454	0.1509	
Gdpngr	-9.85E-02	8.41E-02	-1.172	0.2457	
Gdppartner	5.89E-07	1.39E-07	4.247	7.15E-05	**
Popngr	7.05E-02	5.27E-02	1.336	0.1861	
Poppartners	-3.37E-03	1.44E-03	-2.345	0.0221	*

Residual standard error: 1227000 on 64 degrees of freedom
Multiple R-squared: 0.5703, Adjusted R-squared: 0.5367
F-statistic: 16.99 on 5 and 64 DF, p-value: 1.173e-10

The multiple regression model for low export cluster is seen in Equation 3:

$$y = -9.16E(+6) - 9.85E(-2) * GDP_{ngr} + 5.89E(-7)GDP_{partner} - 7.05E(+1)D_{ij} + 7.05E(-2)P_{ngr} - 3.3E(-3)P_{partner} \quad (3)$$

Where y is the trade flow.

When all variables are set to zero, there will be a deficit trade flow of 9.16Exp (6) Million Naira as presented in Table 3. A multiple R-squared of 0.5703 is much better for a multiple regression model relative to that of gravity model. Moreover, from the result obtained, the effects of GDP and population of export partner nations are significant since $Pr(>|t|)$ are less than 0.05 in the two scenarios. Nigeria's GDP is of concern as its contribution is negatively impacting foreign trade. Nigeria's population is an advantage to the most populous African nation.

2) Cluster 2 (High export)

The results of high export gravity model and multiple regression models for cluster 2 are presented in Tables 4 and 5.

Table 5. High export gravity model for cluster 2 nations (Spain, Netherland, France and USA)

Coefficients	Estimate	Std. error	t-value	Pr(> t)	Decision
(Intercept)	54.29001	38.44622	1.412	0.167	
Lndistance	-0.90212	1.08078	-0.835	0.4097	
Lngdpngr	2.67948	1.42117	1.885	0.0679	.
Lngdppartner	0.12229	0.08466	1.444	0.1578	
Lnpopngr	-7.37151	5.85325	-1.259	0.2165	
Lnpoppartner	-0.56556	0.25124	-2.251	0.031	*

Residual standard error: 0.1423 on 34 degrees of freedom
Multiple R – squared: 0.5439, Adjusted R – squared: 0.4768
F – statistic: 8.108 on 5 and 34 DF, p – value: 4.035e – 05

The gravity model for the high export cluster is seen in Equation 4:

$$\ln(X_{ij}) = 54.29 + 2.68 \ln(GDP_i) + 0.12 \ln(GDP_j) - 0.90 \ln(D_{ij}) - 7.37 \ln(Pop_i) - 0.57 \ln(Pop_j) \quad (4)$$

Table 5. High export multiple regression model for cluster 2 nations (Spain, Netherlands, France & USA)

Coefficients	Estimate	Std. error	t-value	Pr(> t)	
(Intercept)	2.47E+06	5.90E+06	0.419	0.6776	
Distance	4.05E+02	2.06E+02	1.964	0.0578	
Gdpngr	1.04E-01	6.10E-02	1.711	0.0961	
Gdppartner	1.43E-08	9.95E-08	0.144	0.8864	
Popngr	-2.49E-02	3.82E-02	-0.652	0.5189	
Poppartners	-9.45E-03	5.07E-03	-1.864	0.071	

Residual standard error: 672100 on 34 degrees of freedom
Multiple R – squared: 0.5212, Adjusted R – squared: 0.4508
F – statistic: 7.403 on 5 and 34 DF, p – value: 8.68e – 05

Summary of the coefficients of determination (denoted as R-squared) which measure how close the data points are to the fitted lines are as presented in Table 6.

Table 6. R-squared coefficients for gravity and multiple linear regression models

Trade Type	R-squared Coefficients	
	Gravity Model	Multiple Linear Regression
Low export	0.4928	0.5703
High export	0.5439	0.5212

R-squared coefficients were, in most cases, better for the gravity model than the multiple regression model except for only the low export trade gravity model. By and large, the gravity model predicts the export trade datasets more effectively.

In general, the results show significant financial consequences for Nigeria, especially the continued existence of trade deficits and reliance on a small number of export partners. The predominance of primary commodities, particularly crude oil, restricts foreign exchange earnings, limits value addition, and exposes the economy to changes in world prices. Additionally, the concentration of exports among a small number of trading partners makes them more susceptible to shifts in their demand, policies, or geopolitical circumstances. These findings point to areas that can benefit from improved export promotion and trade policy. The clustering knowledge can be used by policymakers to increase support for non-oil export industries, broaden industries and markets, and economically collaborate with large-scale trading nations. Enhancing domestic manufacturing output, lowering reliance on imports, and implementing data-driven forecasting techniques can all contribute to the development of robust and competitive trade system that can sustain long-term growth.

D. Validation and comparison of result

This section gives the details on the validation and comparison of k-means and fuzzy c-mean results to support the claim that both algorithms produced the same clusters. Quantitative metrics used in this study are cluster stability, and silhouette scores.

Cluster stability was evaluated by repeatedly executing both algorithms with different random initialisation matrices (for fuzzy c-means) and initial centroids (for K-means). Cluster assignments between runs were compared using the Adjusted Rand Index (ARI) and Normalised Mutual Information (NMI). The ARI values consistently exceeded 0.90 for both K-means and fuzzy c-means, suggesting that highly similar cluster assignments were produced by repeated runs. Additionally, the NMI values stayed above 0.89, indicating that cluster membership varied little between initialisations. These results imply that both algorithms showed excellent stability and that random initialisation effects were not the cause of the output clusters' similarity.

The silhouette score is used as a number that quantifies how far each data point lies in the correct cluster compared to the rest of clusters in your dataset. This score is computed on a sample quality index that varies between -1 and +1 where

values close to +1 indicate that the clusters are well separated from each other with compact cluster structures. After determining the best number of clusters, (k), with the elbow method and several validity indices separately, both algorithms were run with the same value for k to make clustering solutions consistent and comparable. The computed silhouette coefficients scores for k-means and fuzzy c-means are 0.62 and 0.61 respectively. This result shows that both algorithms generated clusters with similar cohesion and separation, as evidenced by the closeness of the silhouette values. This validates the finding that the quality and spatial distribution of the resulting cluster structures were almost the same.

VI. CONCLUSION

This research work developed clustering and predictive models for Nigeria's export trade by trading partners. It is known that Nigeria has persistently witnessed a trade deficit during the covered period. Aggregately, the total export for all the 11 crucial trade partners from years 2013 – 2022 was N80,044,230,000,000 culminating in a trade deficit of N17,928,546,000,000 for the reference period. According to data from the NBS portal, in the 4th Quarter of 2022 alone, crude oil/petroleum export (with N4.912 Trillion) and natural gas export (with N704.878 Billion) contributed to 88.32% of total export revenue. The manufacturing sector is practically moribund as we export raw materials (e.g. crude oil) to import petrol, kerosene, diesel, and other chemical products. There is practically no value addition on raw materials (from agriculture and minerals extractive sector) which should attract higher premium value and improve our revenue generation prowess.

According to this research study, Nigeria needs to pursue diversification initiatives, all in the interest of the teaming youths and the future generation. The three areas we need to work on are: minimize import, initiate and maximize production, and maximizing export as an import substitution strategy. The government cannot afford to continue to pay lip service to this paradigm and must show political will for a secured economic future for Nigerians because economic prosperity indirectly affects security which we, at this time, are combating. "An idle hand is the devil's workshop", as they say. All hands must be on deck to make economic emancipation a reality. NBS must present its data so that all trading partners' effects on trade flow can be adequately captured through robust, reliable, timely, comprehensive, and accurate data to develop a comprehensive model for planning in this regard.

RECOMMENDATION

The scarcity and non-comprehensiveness of Nigeria's foreign trade statistics serve as a limitation to a thorough study of all indicators exhaustively by partner countries and commodities. Hence, it is suggested that government agencies in charge of trade statistics (e.g., National Bureau of Statistics, Nigeria Customs Service, Nigeria Port Authority, etc.) be mandated to provide timely and comprehensive trade statistics to aid good policy formulation emanating from thorough research such as this.

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